

Section of the conference: Management | Sekcja konferencji: Kierownictwo

How to cite: Singh, S. (2025). Integrating Digitization and Sustainability in Modern Management Practices. *International Conference on Next-Generation Innovations and Sustainability 2025*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15195407>

Integrating Digitization and Sustainability in Modern Management Practices

Dr. Shikha Singh

*Professor, School of Management, Ajeenkya D.Y. Patil University, Pune, India,
dr.shikhasingh5@gmail.com*

Accepted: March 17, 2025 | **Published:** April 1, 2025 | **Language:** English

Abstract: This paper examined integration into the business management practice between digitization and sustainability in the perspective of digital technology contributions to sustainable performance. This study explores the intersection of digital innovation and sustainability, examining current trends, evaluating technological impacts, and identifying both benefits and limitations. While digital tools offer transformative solutions to global sustainability challenges, their implementation must be ethical, inclusive, and mindful of energy consumption and data privacy. Results offer potential through which the application of digital technologies will contribute in altering, improving, and making better sustainability activities by creating innovation, AI and IoT.

Keywords: *Business Dynamics, Digitization, Management, Digital Technologies, (Artificial Intelligence AI).*

Introduction

Today, fast-moving business organizations operate in a scenario wherein technologies develop faster, but the emphasis on sustainability is much stronger. Today, when digitization and sustainability start to converge more significantly for business houses, there is a relevance to keep up in their effort to stay competitive in this transformed world while at the same time, remaining sustainable as well. "Business Dynamics: Integrating Digitization and Sustainability in Management Practices" explores the synergetic interplay of digital transformation and sustainable management practices, how their integration would give rise to new business models, operational efficiency, and sustainable success.

Digitization, due to the increasingly popular trends such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things, is transforming how businesses are performed and the interfaces between businesses and customers. State-of-the-art technologies can better help organizations understand processes, advance supply chains, and make more decisions. At the same time, the sustainability imperative is also gaining more strength globally because environmental degradation and climate change are causing severe resource scarcity pressure on the business world, making it a core component of corporate strategy as sustainability is no longer a peripheral consideration that business must realign their practices toward reducing ecological impact, resource management, and social responsibility. This will be crucial for the business because digital transformation is intimately connected with sustainability in building the power of resilience, long-term growth, and fulfilling the expectations of a growingly conscious global market. Paper will explore how both can be aligned with the management practices of the organization, the challenges, opportunities, and best practices that lead the businesses to the more sustainable and digitally enabled future. Doing this can give the company a way of employing technological power for dealing with the issues on sustainability as the application of sustainable practice provides innovation in excellently producing output.

Research Aim and Research Questions

1. To examine the role of digital technologies in advancing sustainability in 2025.
2. To analyze the benefits and risks associated with implementing digital systems in sustainability contexts.
3. To evaluate the current challenges in modern management practices

Research Results

The study reveals a strong positive relationship between digitalization and sustainability. Firms are implemented digitally moderately with a mean of 3.84 and sustainability practices with a mean of 4.12. The high correlation, $r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$, reveals the significance of AI, IoT, and cloud computing in the application of digital technologies enhancing sustainable practices such as resource efficiency and minimizing waste.

While the above study is contributory, some limitations are; it only targets 100 businesses as a sample while using self-reporting data that may not capture the real occurrences. Future researchers should increase sample size and attempt to explore any long-term digital-sustainability integrations. All in all, this research stresses the transformative abilities of digitalisation in driving a sustainable business enterprise.

Data Analysis begins with a computation of the descriptive statistics; such as the mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions which explain the overall features of data. Below are descriptive statistics summary of the major variables:

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables in Business Management Practices

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range	Min	Max
<i>Extent of Digitalization</i>	3.84	0.78	4	2	6
<i>Degree of Sustainability</i>	4.12	0.69	4	3	7
<i>Integration into Management Practices</i>	4.05	0.74	4	2	7

Source: author's own development

Figure 1

Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables in Business Management Practices

Source: author (s) own development

Extent of Digitalization: The mean score was 3.84, representing a moderate level of digitalization across the sample, and the scores varied from 2 to 6 on a 7-point scale

- Degree of Sustainability: A mean score of 4.12 will suggest the medium or middle-range system to integrate sustainability practices into the business operations, with values ranging between 3 and 7
- Integration into Management Practices: This score of 4.05 shows that most companies have moderately integrated sustainability into their management decision-making

Conclusions

This study discussed the integration of digitization and sustainability in business management practices and how digital tools influence sustainable outcomes and their integration into management strategies. The results indicate that businesses moderately adopt digitalization and sustainability practices, with a significant positive relationship between the two ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). The digital technologies were AI, IoT, and cloud computing, and they were said to be major enablers of sustainability because they enhance the efficiency of resource use and minimize waste. However, the study had limitations such as a small sample size and reliance on self-reported data. Future research should expand the scope to include diverse industries and longitudinal studies to better understand the long-term dynamics of digital-sustainability integration. Overall, this study clearly highlights that digitalization can be transformative in terms of the generation of sustainable business practices and that organizations need to embed sustainability into mainstream strategies, leveraging digital innovations as a path toward success.

References

- Acciarini, C., Borelli, F., Capo, F., Cappa, F., & Sarrocco, C. (2022). Can digitalization favour the emergence of innovative and sustainable business models? A qualitative exploration in the automotive sector. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 15(3), 335-352.
- Agrawal, R., Wankhede, V. A., Kumar, A., Upadhyay, A., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2022). Nexus of circular economy and sustainable business performance in the era of digitalization. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 71(3), 748-774.
- Beusch, P., Frisk, J. E., Rosén, M., & Dilla, W. (2022). Management control for sustainability: Towards integrated systems. *Management accounting research*, 54, 100777.
- Brenner, B. (2018). Transformative sustainable business models in the light of the digital imperative—A global business economics perspective. *Sustainability*, 10(12), 4428.
- Calderon-Monge, E., & Ribeiro-Soriano, D. (2024). The role of digitalization in business and management: a systematic literature review. *Review of managerial science*, 18(2), 449-491.
- Cardinali, P. G., & De Giovanni, P. (2022). Responsible digitalization through digital technologies and green practices. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(4), 984-995.

- Davydova, O., Kashchena, N., Staverska, T. O., & Chmil, H. (2020). Sustainable development of enterprises with digitalization of the economic management.
- Del Giudice, M., Di Vaio, A., Hassan, R., & Palladino, R. (2022). Digitalization and new technologies for sustainable business models at the ship-port interface: A bibliometric analysis. *Maritime Policy & Management*, 49(3), 410-446.
- Hellemans, I., Porter, A. J., & Diriker, D. (2022). Harnessing digitalization for sustainable development: Understanding how interactions on sustainability-oriented digital platforms manage tensions and paradoxes. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(2), 668-683.
- Maffei, A., Grahn, S., & Nuur, C. (2019). Characterization of the impact of digitalization on the adoption of sustainable business models in manufacturing. *Procedia Cirp*, 81, 765-770.
- Miceli, A., Hagen, B., Riccardi, M. P., Sotti, F., & Settembre-Blundo, D. (2021). Thriving, not just surviving in changing times: How sustainability, agility and digitalization intertwine with organizational resilience. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 2052.
- Parida, V., Sjödin, D., & Reim, W. (2019). Reviewing literature on digitalization, business model innovation, and sustainable industry: Past achievements and future promises. *Sustainability*, 11(2), 391.
- Tohănean, D., Buzatu, A. I., Baba, C. A., & Georgescu, B. (2020). Business model innovation through the use of digital technologies: Managing risks and creating sustainability. *Amfiteatru Economic*, 22(55), 758-774.